

than Dhanyalaxmi, 23% higher than Prakash, and 48% higher than IR32 in the wet season and 43% higher than IR32, 22% higher than Prakash, and 14% higher than Laxmi in the dry season. In farmers' field trials, it outyielded Prakash by 38%. Tellahamsa

by 25%, and Samba-Mahsuri by 14%.

Chandan is photoperiod-sensitive, with 145-d duration in the wet season and 155 d (due to low night temperatures) in the dry season in Telangana region. It is resistant to brown planthopper and blast, and moderately resistant to bacterial

blight, sheath blight, and gall midge.

Grain is long slender, straw glumed with small awns, 3.9 L/B ratio. Kernels are white, translucent, flinty, nonglutinous with 10.7% protein content. Cooking quality is good. Up to 55-d-old seedlings can be planted without much yield loss. ■

Integrated germplasm improvement — rainfed lowland

Performance of promising rainfed lowland rice cultivars in West Bengal

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In West Bengal, rainfed lowland rice faces occasional floods and prolonged waterlogging in the wet season. Medium-tall, stiff-strawed, and nonlodging cultivars should do better than traditional varieties.

We evaluated 10 promising lines during 1986 and 1987 wet seasons. The cultivars were transplanted 30 Aug 1986 and 4 Aug 1987 at 20- × 15-cm spacing in 18-m² plots, in a randomized block design. Fertilizer (60-17.6-24.9 kg NPK/ha) was basally applied at transplanting. Water depth during crop growth was 25-30 cm.

Yields and yield attributes of lowland rice varieties and cultures. West Bengal, India, 1986-87.

Cultivar	Days to 50% flowering	Grain yield (t/ha)			Straw yield (t/ha)	Panicles (no./m ²)			Panicle wt (g)		
		1986	1987	Mean	1987	1986	1987	Mean	1986	1987	Mean
CR1030	112	5.2	6.0	5.6	8.9	249	303	276	2.8	3.4	3.1
Pankaj	119	4.4	6.1	5.1	8.6	245	305	225	2.8	2.9	2.9
Jagannath	115	3.7	5.4	4.5	7.4	232	297.5	265	2.2	3.1	2.7
IET7590	122	4.5	7.1	5.8	7.8	242	280	261	3.2	3.3	3.2
IET7044	119	4.4	5.2	4.8	6.6	231	254	242	3.2	3.8	3.5
CR1018	119	4.3	5.4	4.8	7.0	144	283	113	2.9	3.2	3.0
IET7592	122	4.0	6.1	5.6	9.0	205	273	239	2.8	4.5	3.7
CR1016	120	3.7	5.5	4.6	6.7	152	282	217	3.0	3.0	3.0
IET7598	118	4.2	5.4	4.8	6.2	232	281	256	2.6	3.5	3.1
Mahsuri	121	3.8	5.0	4.4	6.5	205	272.5	239	2.5	3.7	3.1
LSD ^a (0.05)		0.8	1.0		1.5	10	ns		0.04	ns	
cv (%)		0.8	7.6		9.3	2	12		0.7	10.6	

^aNS = not significant.

IET7590 had the highest yield (5.8 t/ha), followed by IET7592, CR1030, and Pankaj (see table). Straw yield was highest in IET7592 (9.0 t/ha),

followed by CR1030, Pankaj, and IET7590.

Panicles/m² was highest in CR1030 and panicle weight in IET7592. ■

Two promising high-quality rice breeding lines in Bangladesh

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We crossed C22 with IR9752-136-2 in 1981 at BRRI and developed BR4290-3-1-10 and BR4290-3-3-5 breeding lines.

Both lines have intermediate plant height, short duration, high yield potential, and moderate resistance to lodging and tolerance for drought.

In 3 yr trials at different locations, BR4290-3-1-10 outyielded by an average 45%, local check varieties with similar

Table 1. Some agronomic traits and yield of 2 promising breeding lines in rainfed lowlands. Bangladesh, 1987-89.

Line	Mean plant height (cm)	Mean duration (d)	Mean grain yield ^a (tha)					Mean yield (tha)
			On station		Outreach station		On farm 1989	
			1987 (1)	1988 (5)	1988 (3)	1989 (4)		
BR4290-3-1-10	98	100	1.9	2.0	2.3	3.2	2.5	2.4
BR4290-3-3-5	103	103	2.0	1.9	1.9	2.8	2.3	2.2
BR21 (standard check)	100	103	1.6	-	2.2	2.8	2.4	2.2
Local check	105	100	1.5	1.8	0.9	2.3	1.9	1.6

^aNumbers in parentheses give number of locations.

growth duration (Table 1). BR4290-3-3-5 outyielded local check 31%, with similar growth duration.

Both lines possess higher milling outturn, L/B ratio, and protein percent-

age; intermediate amylose content; and shorter cooking time than check varieties (Table 2).

In 1989 regional farmers' yield trials, the lines showed wide adaptability. ■